

Ingestion of a Metallic Foreign Body in an Adult Patient with Psychosis: Case Report

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Abstract

Foreign body ingestion is a common gastrointestinal emergency that can lead to serious complications, including perforation, obstruction, and infection. This study reviews current management strategies for gastrointestinal foreign body ingestion, emphasizing the importance of prompt assessment and intervention. Both flexible and rigid endoscopy techniques are evaluated, with recent evidence suggesting that flexible endoscopy may be preferred due to its lower complication rates. The consequences of delayed intervention, particularly with sharp objects, are discussed, as delays can result in increased complications. A thorough clinical evaluation, including patient history and appropriate imaging studies, is essential in guiding treatment decisions. This review underscores the necessity of adhering to updated guidelines and optimizing intervention timing to improve patient outcomes in cases of foreign body ingestion. Future research should focus on refining management protocols to further reduce morbidity and mortality associated with gastrointestinal foreign body ingestion.

Introduction

Visits to emergency departments (ED) due to gastrointestinal foreign bodies are relatively common [1,2]. The ingestion or insertion of a foreign object into the gastrointestinal (GI) tract can be a serious medical condition with potential risks for morbidity and mortality [2,3]. Each year, an estimated 1,500 to 1,600 individuals in the United States die from complications related to the ingestion or insertion of foreign bodies into the GI tract [1,3-5]. While this issue can affect all age groups, approximately 80% of cases involve young children (18-48 months), with most incidents resulting from the ingestion of objects like coins, toys, crayons, or pen caps [3,4]. In adults, the ingestion of foreign bodies is less common, usually accidental, and often involves food items such as meat and bones. Other high-risk groups include individuals with psychiatric disorders, edentulous adults, prisoners, and those under the influence of substances that impair judgment [3,5-7]. The clinical presentation, symptoms, and treatment depend on the foreign body's location within

the GI tract. Based on its size and shape, about 80%-90% of foreign bodies pass through the GI tract without complications [4,6,7].

In this report, we discuss the management of a foreign body trapped in the duodenal loop of an adult patient with a psychotic disorder.

Aim of the Article

The aim of this work is to report the clinical management of a metallic foreign body ingestion in an adult patient with psychosis, highlighting the diagnostic approach and therapeutic strategies employed to address this potentially life-threatening condition.

Presentation of Case

This report presents the case of a 33-year-old male patient with a 5-year history of psychiatric disorder, who had discontinued treatment for 1 year and is a chronic smoker. He presented with generalized abdominal pain, vomiting, and mild rectal bleeding for the past 2 days. A thorough anamnesis revealed the ingestion of a rusty fork, which occurred following delusions of persecution.

More Information

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On clinical examination, the patient was in good general condition, hemodynamically and respiratorily stable, and afebrile. Abdominal examination revealed self-inflicted injury marks, a soft abdomen without palpable masses or foreign bodies. Digital rectal examination was unremarkable.

A standard abdominal X-ray revealed a foreign body (a fork with two missing central prongs) located in the left subdiaphragmatic region (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The Standard Abdominal X-Ray Revealing the Foreign Body (Red Circle) Located in the Left Subdiaphragmatic Region

Given the patient's hemodynamic stability, an abdominal CT scan was performed, showing a linear structure at the D2 and D3 levels, generating metallic artifacts that hindered detailed wall exploration, measuring 9x136 mm. This metallic artifact appeared to be in contact with segments I and VI of the liver without signs of peritoneal effusion, pneumoperitoneum, or mesenteric fat infiltration (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The Abdominal CT Scan Slides Showing the Metallic Artifacts at the D2 and D3 Levels

Upon admission, blood tests showed elevated white blood cells at 29,590/mm³ and a C-reactive protein level of 266 mg/L.

The decision of the surgical emergency team was to proceed with surgical exploration. Intraoperative findings revealed no peritoneal effusion or false membranes. After mobilizing the retro-duodeno-pancreatic area, the foreign body was found extending from the genu superius to the genu inferius, causing a 2 cm perforation at the genu superius, which was sealed by the inferior surface of the liver.

The surgical procedure involved the extraction of the duodenal foreign body via a transgastric approach (Figure 3). Antrectomy, including a 2 cm perforation at

the genu superius, closure of the duodenal stump using a TA 60 stapler, gastrojejunal anastomosis in a end to side fashion on a Y loop, passed through the mesocolon, jejunojejunal anastomosis in a end to side fashion at the foot of the loop. Retroanastomotic drainage of the gastrojejunal anastomosis and duodenal stump with Delbet drain; subhepatic, left subphrenic, and right subdiaphragmatic drainage using three suction drains.

Figure 3: Post-Operative Specimen

The postoperative course was marked by a 48-hour stay in the intensive care unit, with drains showing no suspicious fluid. Oral feeding was initiated on postoperative day 5, and the drains were removed on postoperative day 7. A psychiatric consultation was conducted to adjust the patient's treatment, and he was discharged on postoperative day 8. One-year postoperative follow-up revealed no abnormalities.

Discussion

Most blunt ingested objects pass through the gastrointestinal tract without complications, but sharp objects, which account for 5–30% of swallowed items, present a higher risk of perforation. In Asia, where fish consumption is more prevalent, fish bones are a

common cause of lodged foreign bodies as they pass through the GI tract, making up a significant portion of reported ingestions in both adults and children. In contrast, coins are the most frequently ingested foreign objects among children in the United States and Europe, representing about 80% of cases. Among adults, meat impaction is the leading cause of accidental ingestion, often associated with underlying conditions like esophageal stricture or eosinophilic esophagitis. Other accidental ingestions in adults include items like toothbrushes, often used by individuals with eating disorders to induce vomiting. Sharp or multiple objects are more frequently swallowed intentionally. In recent times, adolescent gang initiation rituals have included the ingestion of foreign bodies [8].

Of the objects that require medical attention, 80–90% pass spontaneously, 10–20% necessitate endoscopic removal, and fewer than 1% require surgical intervention. Sharp objects have a significantly higher perforation risk, ranging from 15–35%. Certain objects demand special attention, such as small magnets, which are common in children's toys, and button batteries. One of the most dangerous intentional ingestions involves small packets of drugs, typically swallowed to transport illegal substances. Rupture of a packet, especially of cocaine, can result in fatal outcomes [9].

Sharp foreign bodies carry a higher risk of complications, particularly perforation, which can occur at any point in the gastrointestinal tract but is more frequent in areas of angulation, such as the duodenal C loop and the ileocecal valve. Regions with congenital malformations or prior surgeries are also at an increased risk of bowel perforation following ingestion. Additionally, the likelihood of perforation increases with the number of objects ingested or its pointy forms [10,11].

Which was the case for our patient with the foreign body (FB) incarcerated in the duodenal C loop.

The recommended initial evaluation is based on clinical presentation and simple radiological examinations. A thorough patient history should be taken, including the time of ingestion, type of foreign object, relationship with meal intake, and any history of esophageal diseases. If the patient remains symptomatic, it often indicates obstruction in the esophagus, presenting with varied signs like retrosternal pain, odynophagia, dysphagia, hypersalivation, or aphagia. More concerning signs of complications include fever, tachycardia, subcutaneous emphysema, cervical swelling, abnormal lung sounds, bowel obstruction, or peritoneal syndrome [12,13,14].

Standard radiographs are recommended only for radio-opaque foreign bodies, bony food materials, or unknown objects. Radiographs are also suggested if

complications are suspected, but CT scans are preferable if surgical intervention is being considered. Radiographs with contrast are discouraged due to the risk of aspiration and possible interference with subsequent endoscopic treatment.

Endoscopic management is highly effective, with a success rate of 90–95% and a complication rate of <5%. For food impactions, medical treatment may be considered but should not delay endoscopy. Glucagon (1 to 2 mg IV) is the most commonly used medication, with a success rate of about 35%. Following food impactions, investigations for underlying conditions, such as eosinophilic esophagitis, are recommended. Emergencies are defined by the type and location of the foreign body [15].

In cases where an asymptomatic patient has swallowed a non-hazardous foreign body, outpatient follow-up is appropriate, provided there are no alarm signs. Weekly radiographs can track the progression of the object, with endoscopic extraction if it remains intra-gastric after 4 weeks. However, French guidelines recommend shorter intervention times [16].

Surgical extraction of ingested FBs remains indicated in acute complications that require urgent therapeutic intervention. Mortality associated with FB ingestion has significantly decreased with advancements in endoscopic techniques. It was 57% a century ago, 5% in the 1960s, and has fallen below 1% since 1995 [6,7].

Patients without peri- or post-procedural complications can usually be discharged home shortly after extraction [14].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the management of gastrointestinal foreign body impaction is a critical area in emergency medicine that requires prompt assessment and intervention to minimize complications. The evidence suggests that both flexible and rigid endoscopy are effective techniques, with flexible endoscopy being favored in many cases due to its lower complication rates. However, the timing of the intervention is crucial; delayed endoscopic removal of sharp objects significantly increases the risk of complications, including perforation and mediastinitis. Moreover, thorough clinical evaluation, including the patient's history and imaging studies, is essential in guiding treatment decisions. Understanding the risks associated with different types of foreign bodies and timely endoscopic intervention can lead to improved patient outcomes. Continued research and adherence to updated guidelines are necessary to optimize the management of this condition and further reduce associated morbidity and mortality.

Provenance and Peer Review

Not commissioned, externally peer reviewed.

Consent

As per international standard or university standard, patient(s) written consent has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Ethical Approval

As per international standard or university standard written ethical approval has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Conflicts Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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